

1 **A quantitative methodology for the assessment of the regional** 2 **economic vulnerability to flash floods**

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12

13 **Abstract**

14 Economic losses caused by flash floods are expected to rise worldwide in the coming decades, which is largely
15 due to the increasing exposure of elements at risk. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of the economic context
16 of the potentially affected areas is highly recommendable. Numerous papers have been published to date that
17 focus on quantifying vulnerability in general and in areas affected by floods in particular. However, the number
18 of studies devoted to flash flood-prone areas is far lower. Integrated economic vulnerability assessment enable
19 one to learn what characteristics explain, trigger, intensify, and attenuate the exposure, sensitivity, and
20 resilience of economically vulnerable populations, which can be combined to achieve an Integrated Economic
21 Vulnerability Index (IEVI). The methodology deployed here was conducted in Castilla y León (northwest Spain;
22 94.223 km²) and has allowed the economic vulnerability of urban areas to be analyzed, which has been primarily
23 addressed by the estimation of economic losses or, more recently, including a few economic variables within
24 social vulnerability assessments. Thus, 118 economic variables were initially gathered and then divided into
25 groups through a hierarchical segmentation analysis. Subsequently, variables were combined employing a

26 principal components analysis, giving rise to the economic vulnerability factors that were subsequently
27 aggregated to construct the IEVI. Tolerance statistic was used as a weighting method to define the IEVI,
28 whereas quintiles were chosen as a statistical criterion to map economic vulnerability. As a final step, latent
29 class cluster analysis was implemented to identify spatial patterns of vulnerability. Our findings show that IEVI
30 scores have a high spatial variability and a high degree of complexity in the relationships among different
31 vulnerability factors. Moreover, they help to identify spatial patterns of vulnerability, which makes the design of
32 suitable vulnerability reduction strategies possible, thereby improving the efficiency of flood risk management
33 plans and policies.

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35 Keywords: Economic vulnerability; Vulnerability index; Flash flood risk management; Spatial patterns; Latent class cluster
36 analysis.

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49 **1. Introduction**

50 Over recent decades, population growth, inappropriate land-use planning, environmental degradation, and
51 increases in wealth, together with the effects of global climate change have been found to be the leading causes
52 of the increasing losses caused by the impact of natural hazards (Van Der Veen and Logtmeijer, 2005; Mechler
53 and Bouwer, 2015). Regarding mountainous areas, the increase in the number of flood events and associated
54 losses are primarily due to: (i) the increasing exposure of elements at risk (Fuchs et al., 2015); (ii) natural flood
55 frequency fluctuations (Schmocker-Fackel and Naef, 2010); and (iii) the effects of climate change (Huggel et
56 al., 2012). Flash floods are considered to be one of the natural hazards with the highest capacity to generate
57 risk (i.e., the potential loss of life, harm, or damaged assets which could occur to a society as a result of a natural
58 hazard event, determined by combining hazard, exposure, and vulnerability) (UNISDR, 2016), regarding both
59 the socio-economic and human impact on a global scale (Barredo, 2007; Marchi et al., 2010; Borga, 2013; Terti
60 et al., 2015). The above is mainly due to the fact that flash flood events happen very quickly, which significantly
61 reduces the warning and response times of the population and relevant civil protection agencies (Creutin et al.,
62 2009; Borga, 2013; Bodoque et al., 2015).

63 Despite the efforts of practitioners, decision-makers, stakeholders and public administrations over the last
64 decades to reduce the effects of flash floods, the number of events and associated economic and human lives
65 losses are still increasing all over the world (Birkmann et al., 2013; Munich Re, 2017). This trend highlights the
66 need to continue improving disaster risk reduction strategies. Traditional strategies for reducing disaster risk opt
67 for total control and protection against flood risk, which mainly involves the design and the implementation of
68 structural mitigation measures (e.g. deflection and retention facilities, check dams, levees) (Holub and Fuchs,
69 2009). Such structures are particularly difficult to maintain in mountainous regions due to the limited availability
70 of financial resources, which determines structural protection is usually accompanied by land-use planning and
71 other legal regulations (e.g. building codes, mandatory insurances, risk mapping) (Tompkins et al., 2012;
72 UNISDR, 2015; Papathoma-Köhle and Thaler, 2018), and local structural protection (mainly through an adapted
73 construction design of elements at risk) (Holub and Hübl, 2008; Holub and Fuchs, 2009). Since it is not possible
74 to guarantee complete safety, risk management is currently directed toward recognizing risk and making people
75 aware of and prepared to live with risk (Birkmann et al., 2013; Borga, 2013). The United Nations has been
76 working along these lines since the adoption of the International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (1990-1999)
77 and the subsequent publication of the different frameworks; i.e., the Hyogo Framework for Action (in force until

78 2015) and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (to be developed during the period 2015-2030).
79 Their primary objective is the construction of societies that are more resilient vis a vis the effects of natural
80 hazards in order to reduce human, economic and social losses (UNISDR, 2015). To this end, the development
81 of a system of indicators of disaster risk and vulnerability is viewed as a critical requirement. This approach
82 could help decision makers to assess the potential impact of natural hazards. It could also promote the
83 formulation of appropriate policy responses and identify the most vulnerable social groups and areas (Eakin
84 and Luers, 2006; Birkmann et al., 2013), allowing flood risk analysis and management to be improved (Frazier
85 et al., 2014; Papathoma-Köhle, 2016).

86 Numerous papers focusing on vulnerability have been published in the field of natural hazards (Birkmann et al.,
87 2013; Martín et al., 2017; Wen et al., 2017). Regarding flash floods, approaches followed so far have mainly
88 focused on the physical dimension (Kappes et al., 2012; Zelenáková et al., 2015; Karagiorgos et al., 2016c;
89 Papathoma-Köhle, 2016) and, to a lesser extent, on the social dimension of vulnerability (Balteanu et al., 2015;
90 Aroca-Jimenez et al., 2017; Mahmood et al., 2017). Many flood vulnerability studies have been carried out in
91 large settlements located close to big drainage basins of major rivers, with response times of hours or even
92 days (e.g. Elbe, Danube, and Rhine basins (Fekete, 2009) or South Atlantic Division, USA (Cutter et al., 2013).
93 This is quite a different problem than the one found at small watersheds where flash floods take place. However,
94 to date, research devoted to characterizing economic vulnerability due to flash floods has been scarce. The
95 characterization of this vulnerability dimension could help local decision makers to efficiently manage the
96 available economic resources to deal with flood risk, which can be limited at flash flood-prone areas (Few, 2003;
97 McDowell and Hess, 2012; Khazai et al., 2013). As regards the above, the economic dimension of vulnerability
98 has been mainly addressed through damage estimations, i.e., evaluating replacement economic costs (Fuchs,
99 2009; Karagiorgos et al., 2016a), which does not necessarily reflect the economic vulnerability of a system
100 (Khazai et al., 2013). Other authors such as Van Der Veen and Logtmeijer (2005) evaluated the economic
101 vulnerability of a flood-prone area in the Netherlands through the assessment of the indirect economic costs
102 resulting from a dike failure. However, as stated above, economic costs estimations cannot correctly reflect the
103 economic vulnerability of a place. Assessing vulnerability usually consists of the construction of vulnerability
104 indices representing the inherent characteristics or qualities of social systems that create the potential for harm,
105 i.e., pre-event or pre-existing vulnerability (Cutter et al., 2003, 2008; de Loyola Hummell et al., 2016), as well
106 as considering the static nature of society, i.e., without taking account of daily mobility or activity of people (Terti

107 et al., 2015). In this regard, it is a common practice to include some economic variables in social vulnerability
108 analysis (Cutter et al., 2003; Fekete, 2009; Frazier et al., 2014). Nevertheless, the number of economic variables
109 that are usually included is remarkably reduced, so there can be some aspects of the economic dimension of
110 vulnerability that are not considered, including among them information related to the different economic sectors
111 or utilities (Balteanu et al., 2015; Rahman et al., 2016; Debortoli et al., 2017).

112 The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) defines vulnerability as “the conditions
113 determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the
114 susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards” (UNISDR, 2016).
115 Vulnerability is a function of exposure (i.e., the proximity of people and societal assets to the hazard), sensitivity
116 (i.e., the level of impact the hazard has on people and societal assets) and resilience (i.e., the ability of a
117 community and societal assets to resist, absorb, accommodate, adapt to, transform and recover from the effects
118 of the hazard) (Turner et al., 2003; Adger, 2006; Füssel, 2007). Therefore, vulnerability analysis should consider
119 all the vulnerability dimensions (i.e., social, economic, physical, institutional, cultural and environmental) and
120 components (i.e., exposure, sensitivity and resilience) to assess vulnerability holistically (Karagiorgos et al.,
121 2016b; Papathoma-Köhle, 2016). Numerous papers have been published in which only sensitivity is evaluated
122 (Cutter et al., 2003; Nelson et al., 2015; de Loyola Hummell et al., 2016) or resilience (Cutter et al., 2010;
123 Siebeneck et al., 2015; Qasim et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the use of the integrated approach to assess
124 vulnerability is becoming more frequent, i.e., including all the vulnerability components in vulnerability
125 assessment and analyzing their interactions (Frazier et al., 2014; Terti et al., 2015; Aroca-Jimenez et al., 2017;
126 Lian et al., 2017), which provides a holistic view of vulnerability. Conversely, multi-dimensional vulnerability
127 assessments proposed thus far are only theoretical approaches that recommend key variables of the different
128 vulnerability dimensions, which could serve as a basis for a future methodology, but they do not suggest a
129 practical analysis method (Fuchs, 2009; Menoni et al., 2012; Birkmann et al., 2013).

130 Thus, the objective of this paper is to construct a new economic vulnerability index in urban areas prone to flash
131 flooding, using an integrated approach to assessment. To do that, a set of economic variables were gathered
132 and subsequently analyzed to construct the Integrated Economic Vulnerability Index (IEVI). This analysis was
133 based on applying a sequential statistical multivariate methodology, which included: i) hierarchical segmentation
134 analysis (HSA) to overcome the principal components analysis (PCA) sample size limitation; ii) PCA to extract

135 the vulnerability factors; and iii) latent class cluster analysis (LCCA) to identify economic vulnerability patterns
136 within the urban areas, which helped us to suggest specific mitigation measures for each cluster.

137

138 **2. Data and methods**

139 2.1 Study area

140 The proposed methodology has been tested in the region of Castilla y León, which is an autonomous region of
141 Spain (94,226 km²), representing almost 20% of the country's territory, and one of the largest in Europe (Fig.
142 1). It is located between latitudes 40°05' and 43°14'N and longitudes 1°46' and 7°05'W. Its relief is primarily
143 composed of a set of high altitude plains (called 'Meseta', around 800-900 m a.s.l.) bordered by large mountain
144 ranges (around 2,000 m a.s.l.). The relief produces a predominantly Mediterranean climate with some
145 continental features. The above results in significant thermal and rainfall gradients from the plains to the
146 mountain systems, i.e., from 10 to 2°C for temperatures and from 550 to 1,800 mm for rainfall. Regarding
147 socioeconomic characteristics, Castilla y León has a population of more than 2.5 million. It is administratively
148 divided into 2,248 urban areas, of which more than 84% have a population density of fewer than 20 inhabitants
149 per square kilometer. The rural depopulation that characterizes the region is a factor in the inability of an
150 extraordinary number of mountainous urban areas to maintain resources and provide public services, or the
151 need to cope with high costs to do so (Martínez and Delgado, 2013). On the other hand, the labor dependence
152 ratio in these areas is 0.79, i.e., there are 79 dependents per 100 persons of working age. The ageing
153 population, the livestock and agricultural sectors crisis, and the existing obstacles to generating new economic
154 initiatives result in extremely limited economic dynamism in these urban areas, which highlights the need to
155 properly manage the available economic resources (Molina, 2012).

156

157 **Fig. 1. Location of Castilla y León region and the urban areas studied.**

158

159 **2.2 Database construction: identification of urban areas of interest and selection of economic variables**

160 The first step in implementing the general methodology (Fig. 2) was to identify those urban areas that could be
 161 affected by flash floods. A set of restrictive conditions were implemented for this purpose using ArcGIS v10.1
 162 software. On the one hand, the urban areas that were crossed by rivers with a longitudinal slope higher than
 163 0.01 m.m^{-1} were discriminated (Bodoque et al., 2015). To apply this requirement, a digital terrain model with a
 164 cell size of $200 \times 200 \text{ m}$ provided by the Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN;
 165 <http://centrodedescargas.cnig.es>) was employed to compute river slopes using the Geospatial Hydrologic
 166 Modeling extension (HEC-GeoHMS; <http://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-geohms/>). Meanwhile, the
 167 urban areas that were identified as Areas with Potential Significant Flood Risk (APSFRs) and the hazard areas
 168 with low or exceptional probability of flooding (return period of 500 years) were selected. This cartography was
 169 provided by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment (MAPAMA;
 170 <http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/cartografia-y-sig/ide/descargas/agua/default.aspx>), and they derive from
 171 Directive 2007/60/CE regarding flood risk assessment and management. As a result, 39 urban areas met the
 172 above-mentioned specifications, for which the economic database was created.

173

174

175 **Fig. 2. Graphical overview of the methodology implemented including the construction of the IEVI and the**
 176 **identification of economic vulnerability patterns.**

177

178 In light of existing literature and considering the economic context of the region (Cutter et al., 2003; Merz et al.,
 179 2010; Molinari et al., 2014; Weis et al., 2016; Mahmood et al., 2017), a set of 118 economic variables were
 180 initially described for each of the 39 urban territories recognized previously. Most variables were taken directly
 181 from public databases (e.g. variables related to unemployment by economic sectors or related to dwellings
 182 characteristics or maintenance) or estimated from geographic information (e.g. variables related to lifelines and
 183 infrastructures, such as bridges or sewage treatment plants). Some of them were calculated on the basis of
 184 data from public organizations (e.g. unemployment rate or per capita income). Variables were subsequently
 185 standardized, and a bivariate correlation test was performed to discard redundant variables, i.e., variables with
 186 an absolute correlation coefficient above 0.9 (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014). Finally, 31 variables were employed in
 187 the statistical analysis (Table 1), and these were classified into 5 thematic groups: i) employment and municipal

188 economic situation (7 variables related to the employment situation and economic indicators); ii) private housing
 189 and fleet (11 variables associated with the housing typology and conservation status, and vehicles); iii) public
 190 sector (4 variables linked to public facilities); iv) municipal infrastructures (7 variables related to municipal
 191 facilities and infrastructures); and v) agricultural sector (2 variables linked to the agricultural sector, which is a
 192 key factor in the economy of Castilla y León).

193

194 **Table 1. Groups of variables used in the statistical analysis of economic vulnerability, including data sources and**
 195 **the year of the last data updating.**

Category	Variable	Description	Data source	Year
Employment And Municipal economic situation	UNEMP_RATE	Unemployment rate	Calculated from the number of unemployed and the labor force provided by the Spanish Public Employment Service	2014
	MUN_DEBT	Municipal debt per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	Local entities' current debt (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2014
	PC_INCOME	Per capita income (€/inhab.)	Calculated from the Personal Income Tax sample provided by the Spanish Institute for Fiscal Studies (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2011
	FIXED_INV	Fixed investments per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	Local entities' budget data (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2014
	BUDGET	Municipal budget per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	Local entities' budget data (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2014
	AGRIC_WKS	Number of workers in agricultural sector	Contribution accounts (Regional Statistics Information System)	2015
	ICS_WKS	Number of workers in industry, construction and services sectors	Contribution accounts (Regional Statistics Information System)	2015
Private housing and fleet	M_HOUSES	Main houses	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2011
	S_HOUSES	Secondary houses	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2011
	DWEL_DEF	Dwellings in defective condition	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2011
	DWEL_GOOD	Dwellings in good condition	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2011
	DWEL_1SAGL	Dwellings with 1 story above ground level	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2001
	DWEL_1SBGL	Dwellings with 1 or more stories below ground level	Population and Housing Census (Spanish Statistics Institute)	2001
	TAX_BASE	Tax base of the property tax (in thousands of €)	Property Tax (Spanish Cadastre)	2011
	REPLAC_COSTS	Replacement costs (€/m ²) of dwellings located at flood-prone areas	Calculated from the average home prices and the age (Spanish Cadastre)	2015
	DWEL_FPA	Number of dwellings located at flood-prone areas	Calculated from the information provided by the Spanish Cadastre	2016
	PRIV_VEH	Vehicle fleet	Directorate General for Traffic (Spanish Ministry of Interior)	2014
MA_RS	Mean age of the vehicle fleet	Directorate General for Traffic (Spanish Ministry of Interior)	2014	
Public sector	TOUR_CAP	Tourist accommodation capacity	Tourism infrastructure (Regional Statistics Information System)	2016
	EDUC_INF	Education infrastructures (kindergartens, elementary and secondary schools) located at flood-prone areas	Registration of Non-University Educational Centers (Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture, and Sport)	2015
	RET_HOMES	Retirement homes located at flood-prone areas	Services Guide of Elderly People Residential Care (Spanish Ministry of Health, Social Services, and Equality)	2009

	MONUMENTS	Monuments located at flood-prone areas	Property database (protected Cultural Heritage - Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport)	2016
	LENGTH_STREETS	Length of the streets (meters) located at flood-prone areas	Calculated from the information provided by the Spanish Geographic Institute	2014
Municipal infrastructures	BRIDGES	Bridges located at flood-prone areas	Spanish Topographic Base Map (BTN25; Spanish Geographic Institute)	2009
	STP	Sewage treatment plants located at flood-prone areas	DATAGUA (Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Food, and Environment)	2011
	PROT_RB	Protections of river banks (linear meters) located at flood-prone areas	DATAGUA (Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Food, and Environment)	2008
	RESERVOIRS	Water reservoirs (hectares)	Spanish Topographic Base Map (BTN25; Spanish Geographic Institute)	2009
	TRANSFORM	Electrical transformers located at flood-prone areas	Infrastructure and local facilities survey (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2015
	PARKS	Parks and gardens (m2) located at flood-prone areas	Infrastructure and local facilities survey (Spanish Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations)	2015
Agricultural sector	AGR_MACH	Agricultural machinery	Agriculture (Regional Statistics Information System)	1999
	TGM_AH	Total gross margin of the agricultural holdings (€)	Agriculture (Regional Statistics Information System)	1999

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197

198 2.3 Exploratory analysis of variables

199 The statistical analysis of variables involved two steps (see Fig. 2), which were conducted using SPSS (IBM
200 SPSS Statistics v.19). It is not recommended to perform a PCA when the number of urban areas of interest is
201 not at least three times higher than the number of variables (Maccallum et al., 1999). Therefore, it was necessary
202 to previously implement a hierarchical segmentation analysis (HSA) to overcome this PCA sample size
203 limitation.

204

205 2.3.1 Segmentation of variables into groups

206 HSA is a multivariate statistical technique with the goal of dividing a set of variables into groups (Mooi and
207 Sarstedt, 2014). Whereas a variable in a particular group should be as similar as possible to all the other
208 variables in the same group, it should likewise be as distinct as possible from variables of different groups. The
209 similarity is calculated by estimating the distance between pairs of variables. Variables with smaller distances
210 between one another are more similar, and variables with larger distances are more dissimilar. The squared
211 Euclidean distance was used here as the distance measure, i.e., the sum of the squared differences between
212 variable values (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014). On the other hand, Ward's method was used as a grouping method,

213 which seeks to minimize the within-group variance (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014). This method uses agglomerative
214 hierarchical algorithms. These algorithms follow a hierarchical process, where initially each variable represents
215 an individual group, and they are then sequentially merged according to their similarity. This method is
216 considered to be one of the most effective, especially when the sample size is small (Martín et al., 2015). The
217 graphical output of the HSA (i.e., dendrogram) was used to decide the optimal number of groups in which
218 variables were going to be divided.

219

220 2.3.2 Identification of economic vulnerability factors

221 Once variables were divided into groups, a PCA was performed in each of them. PCA allows the number of
222 variables initially considered to be summarized through the linear combination thereof. They are called principal
223 components or factors and explain most of the variance embedded in the original variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-
224 Olkin (KMO) statistic and the Bartlett's test of sphericity were used to test whether the variables considered
225 were appropriate for performing the PCA (i.e., $KMO > 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, respectively) (Mooi and Sarstedt,
226 2014). PCA uses correlation matrix between variables to extract the factors. Variables that comprise one factor
227 have a certain amount of correlation, while factors are uncorrelated and they cover distinct and unrelated
228 aspects (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014). Factor loadings show the correlation between factors and variables. High
229 factor loadings indicate that a variable is well represented by a specific factor. On the other hand, communality
230 assesses how much of each variable variance is captured by the factors extracted. Variables with communality
231 values below 0.5 were eliminated from the analysis, and the process was replicated. Finally, a least squares
232 regression method was used to calculate factor scores (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014), which were employed to
233 construct the IEVI.

234

235 2.4 Construction of the Integrated Economic Vulnerability Index (IEVI)

236 Factor scores were standardized to a mean of zero, and they took values above or below zero depending on
237 whether urban areas exhibited the characteristics described by a factor above or below the average (Mooi and
238 Sarstedt, 2014). Traditionally, factors that increase vulnerability (i.e., factors associated to exposure and
239 sensitivity component) are introduced into indices as positive values, while factors that decrease vulnerability

240 (i.e., factors related to resilience component) are introduced as negative values (Frazier et al., 2014; de Loyola
241 Hummell et al., 2016). Based on the above, we turned around the sign of some factor scores by multiplying
242 them by -1. Finally, IEVI was calculated using the Eq. 1 (adapted from Frazier et al. (2014):

$$IEVI = E + S - R \quad (1)$$

243 Where *IEVI* is the Integrated Economic Vulnerability Index, *E* is exposure, *S* is sensitivity, and *R* is resilience.
244 Each vulnerability component was estimated according to the Eq. 2 (adapted from Frazier et al. (2014):

$$V_C = \sum_{f=1}^n w_f \cdot P_f \quad (2)$$

245 Where V_C is a vulnerability component (exposure, sensitivity or resilience), w_f is the weight assigned to the f
246 factor, and P_f is the factor score of the f factor. For instance, if a vulnerability component is comprised of three
247 factors ($n = 3$), its value corresponds to the sum of the three factor scores multiplied by their respective weights.
248 The weighting method was based here on the tolerance statistic, which is a statistical test used in regression
249 analysis to detect collinearity (Mooi and Sarstedt, 2014). Thus, those vulnerability factors that were less
250 correlated with the others had a higher weight allocated in the IEVI.

251

252 2.5 Recognition of spatial economic vulnerability patterns

253 Latent Class Cluster Analysis (LCCA) was implemented using the software Latent Gold® 4.5. It is a statistical
254 modeling technique which was performed with the aim of pinpointing economic vulnerability patterns within the
255 study region. LCCA enabled us to identify unobserved heterogeneity by dividing the urban areas of interest into
256 clusters. To do this, a categorical latent variable was created, which indicated the cluster to which each urban
257 area belonged to (Vermunt and Magidson, 2002). The cluster was determined by estimating the probability of
258 belonging to a specific cluster according to the features of the vulnerability factors. Five models were assessed,
259 one (no sample heterogeneity) to five clusters (sample heterogeneity with five patterns) being considered. The
260 optimal number of clusters was determined by the minimum values of the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)
261 and the Consistent Akaike's Information Criterion (CAIC) (Vermunt and Magidson, 2002). Finally, the model
262 profile (i.e., the marginal distribution of values of each vulnerability factor within each cluster) (Haughton et al.,
263 2009) associated with the optimal model enabled us to ascertain the economic vulnerability sources for each
264 cluster identified.

265 **3. Results**

266 3.1 Integrated Economic Vulnerability Index (IEVI) and vulnerability mapping

267 The results obtained in the HSA are displayed in the dendrogram (Fig. 3). Economic variables were divided into
268 five groups after approximately nine iterations of the hierarchical algorithms. These groups contained from 3 to
269 9 variables. Although the groups were not homogeneous in terms of the number of variables, they were coherent
270 regarding the meaning of variables included. Thus, the first group contained variables related to the potential
271 damage to municipal facilities and the labor system. The second group was associated with the individual
272 economic situation and the potential damage to houses. The third group contained variables concerning the
273 potential damage to municipal infrastructures and utilities. The fourth group was composed of variables related
274 to housing type and state of conservation. Finally, the fifth group was made up of municipal economic indicators.

275

276 **Fig. 3. The resulting dendrogram from the HSA. Each dotted-line rectangle shows each of the identified groups,**
 277 **with a total of 5 groups of variables.**

278

279 Performing a PCA in each of the five groups identified by the HSA resulted in the extraction of 8 vulnerability
 280 factors: 1) 'Potential job losses'; 2) 'Urban environment'; 3) 'Economic situation of households'; 4) 'Economic
 281 situation of municipalities'; 5) 'Municipal infrastructures and facilities'; 6) 'Potentially floodable dwellings'; 7)
 282 'Municipal investments'; 8) 'Vehicle fleet'. Factor names were assigned considering the variable loadings within

283 each vulnerability factor, which also allowed them to be categorized by vulnerability component. Thus, exposure
 284 component was made up of factors 2, 5, and 6; sensitivity component included factors 1, 4, and 8; and resilience
 285 component was comprised of factors 3, and 7. The percentage of explained variance was above 50% in all
 286 vulnerability factors. In addition, KMO statistics were higher than 0.6 and Bartlett's tests of sphericity values
 287 were statistically significant (p -value <0.05). Correlation coefficients were shown instead of KMO values in those
 288 cases in which vulnerability factors were formed by two variables, whose coefficients were also statistically
 289 significant (p <0.05 ; Table 2).

290

291 **Table 2. Vulnerability factors identified and main statistical results of the PCA. Variables highlighted in bold**
 292 **correspond to those that have the highest loadings within each vulnerability factor.**

Factor	Variable	KMO/ Corr. (*)	Explained variance	Loading	Factor weight (%)	Factor name	Component		
1	AGRIC_WKS	Number of workers in agricultural sector		0.899		Potential job losses	Sensitivity		
	ICS_WKS	Number of workers in industry, construction and services sectors	0.725	86.589	0.956			7.49	
	TOUR_CAP	Tourist accommodation capacity			0.935				
2	DWEL_FPA	Number of dwellings located at flood-prone areas			0.770	Urban environment	Exposure		
	LENGTH_STR	Length of the streets (meters) located at flood-prone areas	0.786	68.722	0.900			8.01	
	TRANSFORM	Electrical transformers located at flood-prone areas							0.761
	PARKS	Parks and gardens (m ²) located at flood-prone areas							0.876
TAX_BASE	Tax base of the property tax (thousand of €)	0.691							
3	PC_INCOME	Per capita income (€/inhab.)	0.612	61.099	0.792	Economic situation of households	Resilience		
	M_HOUSES	Main houses			0.854				
4	UNEMP_RATE	Unemployment rate	0.617	53.316	0.773	Economic situation of municipalities	Sensitivity		
	MUN_DEBT	Municipal debt per inhabitant (€/inhab.)			0.707				
	REPLAC_COSTS	Replacement costs (€/m ²) of dwellings located at flood-prone areas			0.708				
5	EDUC_INF	Education infrastructures (kindergartens, elementary and secondary schools) located at flood-prone areas			0.766	Municipal infrastructures and facilities	Exposure		
	RET_HOMES	Retirement homes located at flood-prone areas	0.794	63.571	0.773				
	BRIDGES	Bridges located at flood-prone areas			0.796				
	PROT_RB	Protections of river banks (linear meters) located at flood-prone areas			0.852				
6	S_HOUSES	Secondary houses					-0.720	Potentially floodable dwellings	Exposure
	DWEL_1SAGL	Dwellings with 1 storey above ground level	0.624	52.768	0.715				
	DWEL_1SBGL	Dwellings with 1 or more storeys below ground level			0.744				
7	FIXED_INV	Fixed investments per inhabitant (€/inhab.)			0.782(*)	89.077	0.944	Municipal investments	Resilience
	BUDGET	Municipal budget per inhabitant (€/inhab.)	0.944						
8	MA_RS	Mean age of the vehicle fleet	0.328(*)	66.422	0.815	Vehicle fleet	Sensitivity		
	PRIV_VEH	Vehicle fleet			0.815				

293 (*) Correlation coefficients

294

295 Factor scores associated with each vulnerability factor were mapped using the quintiles classification method,
 296 i.e., 20th, 40th, 60th, and 80th percentiles. Five classes were established: i) very high; ii) high; iii) medium;
 297 low; and v) very low (Fig. 4). For exposure and sensitivity factors, red was the color used for the 'very high'
 298 category and blue for the 'very low' category. However, colors were reversed for resilience factors to facilitate
 299 understanding of the map, using blue for the 'very high' category and red for the 'very low'.

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305 **Fig. 4. Mapping of factor scores for each vulnerability factor.**

306

307 Fig. 5 shows the relationships between the IEVI values and their vulnerability components, i.e., exposure,
 308 sensitivity and resilience. Urban areas were colored according to the IEVI values using the quintiles
 309 classification method described above. In this case, red corresponds to 'very high' category (i.e., very high
 310 vulnerability), while blue corresponds to 'very low' category (i.e., very low vulnerability). IEVI defines values that
 311 range from 0.108 to -0.107, the urban areas with the highest IEVI values being located in the west of the region
 312 (León province; see Fig. 1) and the lowest values in the east (Soria province; see Fig. 1). On the other hand,
 313 IEVI values were decomposed into the values of the different vulnerability components, which were represented
 314 using bar charts. Bar heights depend on the vulnerability component values and bar colors indicate the
 315 categories in which the vulnerability component values are found according to the quintiles classification
 316 method. Moreover, bar directions indicate the vulnerability component signs, which depend on whether
 317 vulnerability component values are above component average (i.e., positive values) or below component
 318 average (i.e., negative values).

319

320

321 **Fig. 5. IEVI values and their decomposition into vulnerability components.**

322

323 **3.2 Spatial economic vulnerability patterns**

324 The minimum values of BIC and CAIC determined that the optimal model was the one which considered three
 325 clusters of urban areas (Table 3). The above means that although we would increase the disaggregation level
 326 of clusters (i.e., considering the model with four or five clusters of urban areas) and, thus, the number of
 327 estimated parameters, it would not significantly raise the information explained by the model.

328

329 **Table 3. Statistical summary for the fitted models initially considered.**

	Log-likelihood (LL)	BIC (LL)	CAIC (LL)	Number of parameters
Model 1 (One cluster)	-438.657	935.930	951.930	16
Model 2 (Two clusters)	-325.813	772.523	805.523	33
Model 3 * (Three clusters)	-275.028	733.234	783.234	50

Model 4 (Four clusters)	-257.323	760.105	827.105	67
Model 5 (Five clusters)	-240.470	788.679	872.679	84

330 * Optimal model according to BIC and CAIC values

331

332 The parameters associated to the selected model show that '*Potential job losses*' and '*Municipal investments*'
 333 factors were not statistically significant in dividing urban areas into clusters (p-value > 0.05), so they were not
 334 considered in clusters segregation (Table 4).

335

336 **Table 4. Parameters of the optimal model and associated statistics indicating its ability to differentiate the clusters.**
 337 **Vulnerability factors highlighted in bold were not statistically significant in urban area clustering.**

Vulnerability factors	Cluster 1 (63.1%)	Cluster 2 (25.9%)	Cluster 3 (11.1%)	Robust Wald statistic	p-value	R ²
Potential job losses	-0.371	0.701	-0.329	4.131	0.130	0.223
Infrastructures and real estate	-0.726	0.840	-0.115	17.164	0.000	0.461
Economic situation of households	-0.052	0.770	-0.718	13.435	0.001	0.207
Economic situation of municipalities	0.016	0.490	-0.506	7.678	0.022	0.085
Municipal infrastructures and facilities	-0.647	0.822	-0.176	12.529	0.002	0.405
Potentially floodable dwellings	0.199	0.204	-0.403	7.557	0.023	0.036
Municipal investments	-0.679	-0.736	1.415	4.369	0.110	0.448
Vehicle fleet	-0.121	-0.879	1.000	33.873	0.000	0.284

338

339

340 Finally, spatial patterns were extracted from the model profile. Fig. 6 shows, on the one hand, the cluster to
 341 which each urban area belongs. On the other hand, the representative urban area of each cluster has an
 342 associated bar chart that depicts the profile of each recognized pattern. The representative urban areas were
 343 calculated considering the number of matches between the sign of the vulnerability factors values associated
 344 to each urban area and the sign of the vulnerability factors values associated to each cluster. Bar values
 345 correspond to the standard deviations from the means for each vulnerability factor of each cluster. Moreover,
 346 bar directions reveal the sign of the standard deviation values, which can be positive (i.e., higher exposure,
 347 sensitivity or resilience than cluster mean values) or negative (i.e., lesser exposure, sensitivity and resilience
 348 than cluster mean values).

349

350

351 **Fig. 6. Profile associated to the three detected patterns. Values located above bars correspond to the standard**
 352 **deviation values. Bars of the vulnerability factors considered not to be statistically significant in dividing urban**
 353 **areas into clusters are represented with a meshed plot.**

354

355 Thus, clusters present the following characteristics:

356 - Cluster 1: includes 63.1% of urban areas (a total of 25) and it is characterized by containing urban areas with
 357 the highest values of 'Potentially floodable dwellings' exposure factor and the lowest values of 'Urban
 358 environment' and 'Municipal infrastructures and facilities' exposure factors.

359 - Cluster 2: comprises 25.9% of urban areas (a total of 10) and it is made up of urban areas with the highest
 360 values of 'Urban environment' and 'Municipal infrastructures and facilities' exposure factors. In addition, urban
 361 areas with the highest values of 'Potentially floodable dwellings' exposure factor are also found in this cluster
 362 (i.e., standard deviation values of the 'Potentially floodable dwellings' factor of clusters 1 and 2 are very similar).
 363 Regarding sensitivity component, this cluster contains urban areas with the highest values of 'Economic

364 *situation of municipalities*' factor and the lowest values of '*Vehicle fleet*' factor. On the other hand, this cluster
365 presents urban areas with the highest values of '*Economic situation of households*' resilience factor.

366 - Cluster 3: includes 11.1% of urban areas (a total of 4) and it contains urban areas with the lowest values of
367 '*Potentially floodable dwellings*' exposure factor. Regarding sensitivity component, this cluster is made up of
368 urban areas with the highest values of '*Vehicle fleet*' factor and the lowest values of '*Economic situation of*
369 *municipalities*' factor. Regarding resilience component, urban areas with the lowest values of '*Economic*
370 *situation of households*' factor are found here.

371

372 According to the results described above, it appears that IEVI values are related to the clusters of urban areas.
373 In this regard, an analysis of variance (ANOVA analysis) allowed us to confirm that there were statistically
374 significant differences between the IEVI values of the urban areas of cluster 2 and the other two clusters (i.e.,
375 clusters 1 and 3; p-value < 0.05). In addition, urban areas of cluster 2 are the most vulnerable (IEVI mean value
376 of 0.030), followed by urban areas of cluster 1 (IEVI mean value of -0.008) and urban areas of cluster 3 (IEVI
377 mean value of -0.026).

378

379 **4. Discussion**

380 4.1 Strengths and limitations of data sources and methodology

381 Methodologies for assessing vulnerability and constructing indices vary greatly with data availability and
382 accuracy and the analysis context (Felsenstein and Lichter, 2014; Zachos et al., 2016). Flash floods usually
383 take place in mountainous rivers, affecting small urban areas (Marchi et al., 2010). The statistical information
384 available at this scale is often limited and difficult to obtain and update periodically (Gaume et al., 2009; Ruin et
385 al., 2009), which can sometimes cause that part of the information gathered is out of date and might not be
386 representative (e.g. variables related to the agricultural sector; see Table 1). This means that the selected
387 analysis scale can sometimes be conditioned by data availability and it does not coincide with the appropriate
388 scale for flood risk management (Barnett et al., 2008; Cutter et al., 2013), which could result in an ineffective
389 implementation of vulnerability reduction strategies (Mansur et al., 2016). In addition, the consideration of the
390 analysis context (i.e., the pre-existing social, economic and political conditions) in vulnerability assessments is
391 one of the major challenges for vulnerability researchers (Rufat et al., 2015). Numerous studies published to

392 date include certain variables in their analysis only because they were considered in other papers (see the
393 abovementioned references); however, taking into account the analysis context should entail the adaptation of
394 the selected variables to the local characteristics. Not considering the analysis context can lead to the initial
395 exclusion of representative variables or, conversely, to the overrepresentation of weakly influential variables
396 (Rufat et al., 2015). Analysis context should be considered in the variables selection stage of vulnerability
397 assessments if a reliable representation of observed conditions is pursued (Holand and Lujala, 2013). Thus,
398 variables selected here were considered to be representative of Castilla y León characteristics, taking into
399 account the analysis context in which the study is developed.

400 The methodology most used in the construction of vulnerability indices employs the PCA to extract vulnerability
401 factors from a set of variables initially considered, which are subsequently aggregated to generate indices
402 (Cutter et al., 2003; Frazier et al., 2014; de Loyola Hummell et al., 2016). However, the PCA sample size
403 requirement is rarely considered when formulating vulnerability indices, and variables are often aggregated
404 without any previous processing (Balteanu et al., 2015) or very few variables are considered in the analysis
405 (Rahman et al., 2016). Thus, prior implementation of a HSA allows the PCA sample size limitation to be
406 overcome and, therefore, to develop a robust vulnerability index that can be applied to risk mitigation planning
407 (Tate, 2012). Therefore, the methodology proposed here can be replicated to urban areas with the same
408 problem as it allows performing the PCA without renouncing to include potentially interesting variables.

409 Conversely, the lack of scientific consensus on a general methodology for assessing vulnerability has resulted
410 in high variability regarding how to address each of the stages of the vulnerability index development process
411 (Tate, 2012) and cartographic results (de Loyola Hummell et al., 2016; Papathoma-Köhle, 2016; Aroca-Jimenez
412 et al., 2017). Consequently, it is very difficult to compare the results of vulnerability assessments from different
413 study areas. In fact, index scores should only be used to qualitatively contrast if an urban area is more or less
414 vulnerable than another (Cutter et al., 2013). Moreover, the development of alternative methodologies for factor
415 weighting represent a key research need (Rufat et al., 2015). Assuming that 'all vulnerability factors are equal
416 in weight' has been the most used approach thus far to establish vulnerability indices (Cutter et al., 2003;
417 Chakraborty et al., 2005), although some papers have already pointed out that not all factors have the same
418 importance in the index construction (Eakin and Luers, 2006; Liu and Li, 2016). Use of context-specific weights
419 from expert opinion survey methods could be one path toward better weighting approaches. However, this
420 scheme is considered to be a time-consuming and costly process by other authors (Rufat et al., 2015). Thus,
421 the weighting methodology proposed here, which is based on the tolerance statistic, might be regarded as a

422 suitable alternative in this context (Aroca-Jimenez et al., 2017). Conversely, validation of vulnerability indices is
423 a key aspect of vulnerability analysis. The aim of the validation is to test the validity of a vulnerability index, and
424 it is usually addressed by using a supplementary dataset of existing information about real extreme flood events,
425 e.g. property damages, fatalities, frequency of disaster declarations (Fekete, 2009; Bakkensen et al., 2017).
426 However, and particularly in the case of flash flood events, these data are not usually available, so validation is
427 difficult to address in this context.

428 It is also worth highlighting that a vulnerability index constitutes a snapshot view (Frazier et al., 2014), although
429 vulnerability varies spatially and temporally (Eakin and Luers, 2006; Rufat et al., 2015). Vulnerability has a very
430 high spatial variability, so it is necessary to include the spatial patterns of vulnerability in the design of risk
431 management plans in order to make optimal decisions (Koks et al., 2015). Identification of spatial patterns of
432 economic vulnerability carried out here through the LCCA is an improvement in this regard. This approach could
433 help the competent regional authorities to conduct more effective flood risk management (Aroca-Jimenez et al.,
434 2017). Regarding the temporal context, monitoring those variables originally included in vulnerability
435 assessments would be necessary (Eakin and Luers, 2006). The above would inform decision makers about
436 how index values vary over time (Ge et al., 2013) and it would enhance our understanding of the interactions
437 between vulnerability factors (Rufat et al., 2015).

438

439 4.2 Integrated assessment and economic vulnerability patterns

440 Economic vulnerability is usually assessed in conjunction with social vulnerability (Cutter et al., 2003; de Loyola
441 Hummell et al., 2016), although the number of variables related to the economic dimension is much lower than
442 the number of social-related variables, especially in assessments carried out in urban areas prone to flash
443 flooding (Balteanu et al., 2015; Terti et al., 2015; Karagiorgos et al., 2016b, 2016c). Vulnerability is mainly
444 determined at community level by diversity of economic assets, access to resources, and relative distribution of
445 income (Adger, 1999; Rufat et al., 2015), which means that the causes of vulnerability are fundamentally related
446 to the economic context. Nevertheless, no publications have been found in international literature on assessing
447 economic vulnerability by taking into account the context. Identifying economic vulnerabilities is even more
448 important in urban areas affected by flash floods due to the fact that they are usually rural populations with low
449 availability of services, infrastructures and economic resources (Pelling, 1999).

450 Vulnerability factors obtained here are considered to reflect the economic vulnerability of the region (see Table
451 2). Moreover, vulnerability factor mapping helped us to establish relationships between their spatial distribution
452 and the economic characteristics of the region (see Fig. 4). So, exposure component is composed, on the one
453 hand, of the factors '*Urban environment*' and '*Municipal infrastructures and facilities*' (Fig. 4b, 4e). They are
454 mainly related to the potential damages caused in flood-prone areas, e.g. potential cleaning-up costs of the
455 streets affected or potential repair costs of the education infrastructures or retirement homes affected. The great
456 majority of urban areas included here act as county seats, i.e., urban areas with basic infrastructures and
457 services which connect smaller areas that lack them. Therefore, infrastructure damages or service interruptions
458 could also affect those areas that depend on these county seats, which would increase consequences. On the
459 other hand, the '*Potentially floodable dwellings*' factor is mainly related to the potential damages at individual
460 level (Fig. 4f), affecting main houses with only one story above ground level, which usually have the lowest
461 floors located at ground level (Bodoque et al., 2016b). The above means that dwellers cannot move their
462 belongings to a safer place (e.g. to the second floor of their homes) to reduce potential economic consequences.

463 Regarding the sensitivity component, it is related firstly to the economic capacity of urban areas to deal with
464 flood consequences through the factors '*Potential Job Losses*' and '*Economic situation of municipalities*' (Fig.
465 4a, 4d). Urban areas have major significance for the services sector, especially in relation to trading and tourism.
466 In this context, if tourist accommodation is damaged by flash flood events (Weis et al., 2016), not only should
467 repair costs be considered; it could also lead to the temporary loss of profits, both for owners and municipalities
468 (Delgado et al., 2012). The same can be stated regarding the interruption of trade flows. Furthermore, these
469 urban areas show high unemployment rates and high municipal debt levels, so they have low (individual and
470 collective) economic capacity for facing possible replacement costs caused by a flash flood event (Fekete, 2009;
471 Frazier et al., 2014), which would require external financial support in the recovery process (Fatemi et al., 2017).

472 Secondly, the factor '*Vehicle fleet*' (Fig. 4h) reflects the wealth level of the urban areas (Weis et al., 2016). Urban
473 areas with the highest values in this factor correspond to the most depopulated areas, characterized by low
474 population densities, high dependency rates, and almost without economic activity (Delgado et al., 2012; Aroca-
475 Jimenez et al., 2017), so they would also need external aid and financial support in emergency and recovery
476 processes.

477 Finally, the resilience component is related, on the one hand, to citizens' capacity to cope with flash flood
478 consequences ('*Economic situation of households*' factor). Urban areas that have the highest values in this
479 factor (Fig. 4c) correspond to the most developed areas where industry, construction and services sectors

480 predominate; in contrast to those areas where agricultural activities predominate, which correspond to least
481 economically active areas (Delgado et al., 2012). These areas have a high capacity to resist, cope with and
482 recuperate from flash flood events due to their economic capacity for implementing preventive measures at
483 household levels (de Loyola Hummell et al., 2016; Fatemi et al., 2017). On the other hand, urban areas with the
484 highest values in the factor *Municipal investments* (Fig. 4g) are in a good economic situation, so they could
485 allocate part of the municipal budget to the implementation of mitigation measures to reduce flash flood-related
486 losses and even to develop a system of financial aid in order to help the population to overcome floods'
487 economic consequences (Fekete, 2009; Koks et al., 2015).

488 Integrated economic vulnerability analysis also enables us to know how exposure, sensitivity and resilience
489 interact and their relationships with IEVI values (Fig. 5). Urban areas with the highest IEVI values show highest
490 values of exposure, but there is no predominance of certain categories of sensitivity and resilience components.
491 The above is due to the fact that there is a great variability of combinations for the intermediate categories of
492 the IEVI values, so it is difficult to distinguish economic vulnerability patterns. Finally, urban areas with the lowest
493 IEVI values show the highest levels of resilience, coinciding generally with the lowest values of exposure and
494 sensitivity components. Thus, integrated economic vulnerability assessment allows us to suggest more effective
495 vulnerability reduction strategies focused on reducing exposure and sensitivity and on reinforcing resilience.

496

497 4.3 Implications for flood risk management and policy

498 Identification of spatial patterns of economic vulnerability was the main goal of the LCCA (Fig. 6). Urban areas
499 included in the same cluster share characteristics, so it can help decision makers to develop more successful
500 flood risk management strategies at regional level. Different vulnerability reduction strategies can be proposed
501 for each cluster. For example, in cluster 1 vulnerability reduction should be targeted towards individual
502 protection. Thus, in response to an emergency, dwellers should try to protect their assets at risk taking them to
503 higher positions above floor level. In cluster 2, vulnerability reduction should be focused on creating a municipal
504 system of incentives to encourage inhabitants to carry out mitigation measures at the household level (Holand
505 and Lujala, 2013; Zhou et al., 2014). Finally, in cluster 3 vulnerability reduction should be targeted towards
506 building municipal economic support funds to help affected inhabitants (after a flash-flood event) during the
507 recovery phase (Schelfaut et al., 2011). On the other hand, considering that urban areas included in cluster 2
508 are the most vulnerable (see Section 3.2) could help decision makers to set priorities in allocating the available

509 economic resources to vulnerability reduction, which should be mainly intended for encouraging the population
510 to protect themselves, as stated above.

511 Thus, the IEVI and the identification of spatial vulnerability patterns constitute a significant step towards
512 improving flood risk management (Frazier et al., 2014; Papathoma-Köhle, 2016), since they enable tailored
513 flood risk mitigation strategies to be designed for each urban area (Koks et al., 2015). However, it is necessary
514 to effectively communicate these improvements to the different stakeholders if integrated flood risk management
515 is expected (Phillips and Morrow, 2007; Kubal et al., 2009). Target groups should include decision makers,
516 emergency managers, disaster responders and, most importantly, society (Kubal et al., 2009). The above is
517 even more important in those areas prone to flash flooding, where the response time is shorter (Bodoque et al.,
518 2016a; Karagiorgos et al., 2016c). Vulnerability analysis can help civil protection agencies to prioritize their
519 actions in managing emergency situations and to help insurance companies to give the most vulnerable urban
520 areas priority in evaluating economic damages. In Spain, the Insurance Compensation Consortium (CCS) acts
521 as the central figure of the compensation system after the occurrence of extraordinary risks, including flash
522 floods. The CCS covers damages to persons and direct material damages, as well as the loss of profits arising
523 from the direct damages, provided that those affected have insurance policies previously contracted with private
524 insurance companies, without requiring the official declaration of 'catastrophe' or 'disaster area', as happens in
525 other countries (Surminski et al., 2015).

526 Regarding flood risk management in Spain, it is worth mentioning that after the period characterized by the
527 development of extensive infrastructure to mitigate flood risk, land-use planning appeared to be a rational, cost-
528 effective, and sustainable alternative for reducing flood risk at regional and local level. However, during the "real
529 estate bubble" (1995-2007), Spain underwent a high increase of exposure to flood risk due to the indiscriminate
530 occupation of flood-prone areas (Pérez-Morales et al., 2018), when many town councils received large amounts
531 of money from building permissions without adequately controlling the suitability of lands for urbanization. The
532 transposition of the European Floods Directive into the Spanish legislation in 2010 was a turning point in the
533 situation described above. As a result, national and regional legislation on land-use planning already require
534 developing flood risk maps in order to determine if lands are adequate to be urbanized or not. So, flood risk
535 maps have become an essential tool for land-use planning also in Spain. Despite in Spain, there is no specific
536 legislation on adapting buildings or infrastructures to floods; however, there are some briefing (i.e. nonbinding)
537 documents that provide a series of measures to protect and recover from a flood. The methodological

538 approaches contained in these documents could be implemented at local level (e.g. the Spanish Civil Protection
539 Plan, the Flood Risk Management Plans, or the Guide for vulnerability reduction of buildings against floods).

540 Integrated vulnerability assessments, and therefore the resulting indices, can also help the appropriate
541 allocation of economic resources (which are usually limited in urban areas affected by flash floods) to
542 vulnerability reduction (Rufat et al., 2015; UNISDR, 2017) and to the spatial delimitation of 'catastrophe zones'
543 in order to assign properly the corresponding disaster financial compensations by the public administration. In
544 addition, risk reduction should be a key aspect of local development, which could contribute to the revitalization
545 of the local economy (Liao, 2012; UNISDR, 2017). This point is very important in the context of Castilla y León
546 because there are many urban areas that have significant problems equipping themselves with the necessary
547 facilities and providing basic services to the local population (Delgado et al., 2012), which increase vulnerability
548 (Rufat et al., 2015).

549 Social perception and awareness determine the effectiveness of flood risk mitigation and emergency plans since
550 they enable suitable risk communication and education plans to be devised to improve community resilience
551 (Micu et al., 2015; Bodoque et al., 2016a). Comprehensive flood risk management requires, in addition to an
552 integrated vulnerability analysis, the drawing up of risk communication plans to inform the population about how
553 they should proceed (or how they should not) when facing a flash flood event. Finally, the participation of the
554 population in the formulation of vulnerability reduction strategies not only reduces the possible economic
555 damages caused by a flash flood, but also increases the efficiency of flood risk management plans and enables
556 the communities to be empowered and gain ownership (UNISDR, 2017), which would result in an increase in
557 community resilience.

558

559 **5. Conclusions**

560 Obtaining a truly reliable IEVI requires the implementation of a robust methodology for its construction. However,
561 in geographical contexts where available information is limited, as usually occurs in urban areas prone to flash
562 flooding, the appropriate ratio between the number of urban areas considered and the number of variables to
563 perform the PCA is rarely taken into account. Application of the HAS previously to applying PCA allows this
564 limitation to be addressed and represents an alternative to the methodology usually used to construct
565 vulnerability indices in these areas. Meanwhile, the integrated vulnerability analysis allows the direction and
566 intensity of the interactions between the different vulnerability components and between these and index scores

567 to be ascertained. The results obtained here show major complexity in these interactions and a high spatial
568 variability of IEVI values. This highlights the importance of conducting integrated assessments. The IEVI
569 enables the vulnerability component that should be enhanced or strengthened for each urban area to be
570 identified. This can help competent authorities to suggest more effective vulnerability reduction strategies. The
571 identification of spatial patterns by means of the LCCA enables the design of more appropriate vulnerability
572 reduction strategies for each of the differentiated clusters of urban areas, which would also help to allocate
573 economic resources more efficiently and therefore to improve FRM policies and plans at the regional scale. In
574 addition, the results of the LCCA allows the spatial information to be synthesized into a single map; this can be
575 a very useful tool to connect the vulnerability analysis with decision-making authorities.

576

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582

583 **Declarations of interest**

584 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

585

586 **Author contribution**

587 E. Aroca-Jimenez created the database and wrote the manuscript with contributions from all the co-authors.
588 Jose M. Bodoque designed the research and critically revised the manuscript. Juan A. Garcia conceived the
589 statistical procedure, which was carried out by E. Aroca-Jimenez and J.A. García. A. Díez-Herrero acutely
590 reviewed the manuscript and designed Figure 2.

591

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